

Appendix A

Wellness Days Qualtrics^{XM} Questionnaire

1. Were you aware that your program has granted you 2 “wellness days” per year to take for your general health maintenance?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
2. How many of these days did you take during this academic year?
 - a. 0
 - b. 1
 - c. 2
3. How far in advance did your program require notification before taking these days?
 - a. 0-7 days
 - b. 8-30 days
 - c. More than 30 days
 - d. No requirement

For each of the wellness days that you took, please indicate the reason.

4. Day 1
 - a. Dental appointment
 - b. Doctor’s appointment
 - c. Family obligation
 - d. Personal - other
 - e. Choose not to answer
 - f. NA – I did not take this day
5. Day 2
 - a. Dental appointment
 - b. Doctor’s appointment
 - c. Family obligation
 - d. Personal - other

- e. Choose not to answer
 - f. NA – I did not take this day
6. If you did not take any or all of these wellness days, please indicate the reason why?
- a. I did not know they were available
 - b. I had no particular need for them
 - c. I personally did not want to burden my program
 - d. I was discouraged by my program from taking them

Please provide some general demographic information

7. Please indicate your level of training

- a. CY1
- b. CY2
- c. CY3
- d. CY4
- e. CY5
- f. FEL1
- g. FEL2
- h. FEL3

8. Gender

- a. Male
- b. Female

9. Age

- a. 20-25
- b. 26-30
- c. 31-35
- d. 36-40
- e. 41-45
- f. 46+

10. Married

- a. Yes

b. No

11. Children

a. Yes

b. No